

Senior High School Teacher's Assessment on Multiliteracies Practices across Strands

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Abstract: At present, twenty-first century, multiliteracies refers to one of the major aspects of language use in which meaning is created in increasingly multimodal ways. It is a way of students to comprehend information and creating meaning by manipulating individual modes of interaction and meaning making. Tan and Ang's (2020) findings revealed that teachers had difficulty engaging students in meaningful multiliteracies practices. The study's purpose was to identify the various multiliteracies practices of senior high school teachers across strands at a Philippine university, as well as to provide multiliteracies guidelines for lesson planning. The researchers evaluated the teachers' practices using a descriptive quantitative research design. The respondents were 43 teachers from five learning areas: Research, English and Humanities, Philosophy and FCL, Science and Mathematics. As an assessment tool for the teachers' practices, a validated researcher-created questionnaire was used. The findings revealed that in the Science Learning Area, teachers demonstrated their ability to check students' retention of discussed topics through oral presentations, recitations, and games with a mean average of 3.83, whereas in the Math Learning Area, teachers used organized informational texts, instructional videos, and lecture discussions with a mean average of 3.88. Furthermore, all of the other teachers from various learning areas have used various multiliteracies practices in their lessons. It is concluded that senior high school teachers from various learning areas use multiliteracies in their classrooms. A multiliteracy lesson planning guideline was developed to serve as a model.

Keywords: *Multiliteracies, Lesson Plan.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Multiliteracies states the concept of how will the students understand information and the design of meaning through the manipulation of individual modes used in interaction and meaning making. In the study of Tan and Ang (2020), teachers encountered difficulty in engaging the learners in meaningful multiliteracy practices. This study will focus on the Modal literacy and the researcher intends to propose a guide for lesson planning to make learning more flexible and cater the needs of the learners on the new dimensions of learning and multimodal way of communication.

Teachers in higher education must have and possess knowledge of "language and literacy as well as being skilled at acquiring and analyzing material, and be able to impart these understandings to their learners" (Heydon 2005, as cited by Navehebrahim 2011). In the 21st century, the learners need to be proficient on multimodal way of communication and

receive information through different mediums. Hence, the teachers must also adopt and provide opportunities on how the learners will develop multiliteracy.

The New London Group developed multiliteracy in 1994, incorporating a variety of linguistic, cultural, communicative, and technological approaches to address how technology changes and how globalization affects education. This assists students in preparing and adapting to construct knowledge in a variety of social contexts and communicating through various means of recording and transmission. Seel, (2012), as cited by UNESCO stated that the idea of multiple literacies is focused on the idea that people must also learn to create meaning from variety of sources and different ways of representing information through different modes. This study highlighted one way on how multiliteracies can be viewed as stated in the article *The Importance of Multiple Literacies, Modal Literacies and Literacy by Medium*. This study focused on the Modal literacy and the researcher intends to

propose a teaching model to make learning more flexible and cater the needs of the learners on the new dimensions of learning and multimodal way of communication.

Research findings show that multiliteracy, specifically the multimodal ways are crucial in the learning process of the learners in the 21st century. Ang and Tan (2020) cited that by incorporating what is already known, pedagogy enhances the teaching and learning process new in the current setting. As a result, it is critical for educators to have experience with multimodal learning for students. Multimodal education facilitates the use of modern methods and media designed to capitalize on various technological devices and multimedia. Furthermore, regardless of their potential, the genres and literacies produced by the younger generation are influencing their future. Shoffner et al. (2010), stated that adolescent literacy is becoming a more difficult issue in secondary English education because teachers continue to discuss reading and writing as the primary areas of focus in schools all over the world, but they also work with alternative texts, current media, well-known photographs, and educational technologies. According to Tricamo (2020), students will benefit from various teaching modalities as well by establishing links between what they learn in class and their surroundings and recognizing their role as forerunners of the social future.

In accordance with discipline objectives and ideologies, Tricamo (2020) came to the conclusion that the future of educational scholarship should concentrate on multiliteracies in the subject areas and provide additional framework for multimodal learning. According to Jewitt's research from 2005, students' interaction with a range of media, such as images, animation, hypertext, and layered multimodal texts, reshapes their interpretive work. Additionally, it is recommended that teachers may address diversity inside the classroom through the use of multi modal texts, redesigning, or the explicit teaching. The primary picture of semiotic resources, for example, can be the focus of explicit lessons that teachers can design using a variety of modal resources.

Jacobs (2013), contends that teachers must focus more on how students will be engaged through the different approaches the teacher has to offer. In multiliteracies, it is very important for the teachers to observe how students will be engaged to be able to lead a to a new way of creating information through the use of multimodal modes. The author suggested that every assessment should be ongoing and formative. Instead of evaluating students' final summative projects, teachers should be looking for indicators that demonstrate their learning throughout their text- and multimodal-project creation in continuous educational environments. Therefore, in addition to focusing on the learning outcomes, educators also need to take into account the process and the enactment.

Tsang (2015) presented a three-phase model for a more comprehensive understanding of literacy in science classes, including harnessing youth's cultural, scaffolding multimodal practices, and hybridizing a third space. The model's initial phase is devoted to investigating the natural world. Moreover, Bintarik, Yuniawatika, & Untari (2018) concluded that the developing of scientific learning models based on multiliteracies can increase student activities with multi-context, multimodal and multicultural.

This study utilized the Theories of Multiliteracies created by the New London Group in 1994 which is the source of modalities of meaning making to serve as framework for understanding on how to use the semiotic modes effectively. The theoretical aspects of multiliteracies were discussed by Cole and Pullen in 2009. As previously mentioned, Bill Cope and Mary Kalantzis from the New London Group, who developed multiliteracies, presented their argument in chapter 5 of the book, "New media: New learning." The authors argue that the widespread use of new media on a global scale has profoundly changed how people learn. the digital applications of various information and communication technologies that make up new media. On the other hand, the theoretical framework for multiliteracies was developed by David R. Cole and Darren L. Pullen by examining the ways in which students absorb information from contemporary life. Last but not least, David R. Cole wrote the book *Politics of Desire*, which was included in the theoretical section of the multiliteracies final chapter. According to the author, the integration of media technology into the classroom has influenced how people view teachers' work in the modern educational setting. This theory will be of help in creating a guide in incorporating theoretical aspects of multiliteracies such as new media, students' modern life and influence on teachers' work in lesson planning.

Tricamo (2021) stated that the use of multiple modes in teaching will also allow students to draw connections on what they have learned in school and the world around them. This study will provide significant change to students' learning outcomes such as building up necessary skills in meaning making and understanding social, cultural and linguistic experiences inside and outside of their classrooms. It will also allow teachers to develop more on their way of multimodal way of teaching, professional development and enactment of multiliteracies. Lastly, this study will provide a different avenue for the future researchers to provide the necessary teaching strategies for diverse students at present in the 21st century.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study determined the multiliteracy practices of senior high school teachers across strands and used as basis for lesson planning for Senior High School classroom.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

- Determine the senior high school teachers’ multiliteracy practices
- Provide a multiliteracies guideline for lesson planning

III. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research was used in this study to outline the characteristics of a population. This design aided in evaluating teachers' multiliteracy practices in senior high school classrooms.

This research took place at the University of Perpetual Help - Molino Campus SHS. Bacoor City, Cavite, Molino 3. The respondents were all the teachers from different learning areas (Research, English, ABM, TVL, Filipino, Math,

Philosophy and FCL and Science) chosen through availability sampling. Five out of eight learning area participated in the study due to some conflict in the schedule. A researcher-created instrument was used to evaluate respondents' practices on multiliteracies. The researcher was able to distinguish the teachers' practices on multiliteracies in all strands using this sample. A researcher-made questionnaire which was subjected to validity and reliability test by three English teachers was used to gather data from the respondents. The questionnaire was an assessment tool use to evaluate the practices of teachers on multiliteracies in a lesson. It consisted of evaluation criteria that measured the skills from Highly Practiced to Not Practiced at All.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter features findings, discussions, and multiliteracies strategies used by senior high school teachers in various subject areas.

A. Senior High School Teachers Multiliteracies Practices

Table 1 Science Department

STATEMENTS	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTOR
12. I check students’ retention of discussed topic through oral presentations, recitations, and games.	3.83	HIGHLY PRACTICED
13. I ask the learners to demonstrate what they have learned through activities that will require them to use of new media (podcasts, discord, etc.).	2.75	PRACTICED
14. I let the students share their works in various platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Blogspot, Word Press, Pinterest, YouTube etc.	2.75	PRACTICED

Table 1 shows that teachers in Science Learning Area highly practice the 12th indicator which is checking of students’ retention of the discussed topic through oral presentations, recitations, and games with a mean of 3.83 while in the teachers practice 13th and 14th indicator with a mean of 2.75.

This finding is in contrast with Tsang's (2015) study on scaffolding multimodal disciplinary practices, which examined how popular media texts were organized and formulated in accordance with interests, values, and ideologies to observe multimodality in science classrooms. In order to help students make sense of scientific terminology, teachers in science classrooms must keep incorporating different platforms with related topics.

The findings show that teachers in the Science Learning Area continue to use traditional teaching strategies in their classes, such as topic recall, recitations, and motivational exercises. In order to demonstrate multimodality in the classroom, teachers must also make the most of the new media available to them. Teachers need to use a variety of platforms to keep students engaged, as the study mentioned above. It is crucial that students are able to practice understanding the terminologies by using the various platforms once they have demonstrated mastery of the lesson.

Table 2 Math Department

STATEMENTS		MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTOR
2.	I provide an organized informational texts, instructional videos and lecture discussions.	3.88	HIGHLY PRACTICED
14.	I let the students share their works in various platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Blogspot, Word Press, Pinterest, YouTube etc.	2.00	SOMEWHAT PRACTICED

Table 2 shows that teachers in Math Learning Area highly practice the 2nd indicator which is providing an organized informational texts, instructional videos and lecture discussions with a mean of 3.88 while the 14th indicator which is letting the students share their works in various platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Blogspot, Word Press, Pinterest, Youtube etc. is somewhat practiced with a mean of 2.00.

In line with the study of Takeuchi 2015, the study describes the context that enabled English Language Learners (ELLs) to participate successfully in mathematics classroom activities. It draws attention to the teacher's affirmation of the students' identities as multimodal users, as well as her use of several languages and tangible and symbolic tools.

This suggests that instructors in the Math Learning Area will keep incorporating context-based learning materials and lecture-based discussions into their lessons. Students studying mathematics in the classroom must also practice using the various platforms to share what they have learned and support other students who are having difficulty understanding particular math lessons.

Table 3 Research Department

STATEMENTS		MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTOR
2.	I provide an organized informational texts, instructional videos and lecture discussions.	3.80	HIGHLY PRACTICED
3.	I raise global issues through video presentations and facilitate collaborative tasks.	3.80	PRACTICED
4.	I verbally explain the lesson with a clear and well-modulated voice, formulate questions and provide printed materials using my own lay-out.	3.80	HIGHLY PRACTICED
5.	I let the students relate the lesson to their daily lives through photographs, video presentations, and role playing.	3.00	PRACTICED
10.	I teach them how to use various credible sources for them to verify information.	3.80	HIGHLY PRACTICED
12.	I check students' retention of discussed topic through oral presentations, recitations, and games.	3.80	HIGHLY PRACTICED
15.	I provide opportunities for meaningful interaction, enumerate significant points, and reflects on the significance through creative presentations.	3.80	HIGHLY PRACTICED

Table 3 shows that Research Learning Area highly practice 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 10th, 12th, and 15th indicator with an average mean of 3.80 while the 5th indicator which is letting the students relate the lessons to their daily lives through photographs, video presentations, and role playing is practiced with an average mean of 3.0.

This study conforms with that of Kaur and Sudhar (2015), who came to the conclusion that using technology in the classroom encourages learner-centeredness and departs from the passive classroom listening format that has been prevalent in many Malaysian classrooms for the past few decades. This is a defining feature of the multiliteracies approach, in which learners enhance their English literacy on their own.

The findings show that when teaching research subjects, teachers in the Research Learning Area put multiliteracies into practice. In order to implement student-centered learning, teachers in the Research Learning Area use well-organized informational texts, instructional videos, and lecture discussions. They also teach students how to verify information using a variety of reliable sources, create opportunities for meaningful interaction, list important points and reflect on their significance through creative presentations, and assess students' retention of the material through games, oral presentations, and recitations.

Table 4 English Department

STATEMENTS	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTOR
11. I allow the students to discuss a topic in a creative way through video presentations, role playing, jingles, games, and many others.	4.00	HIGHLY PRACTICED
12. I check students' retention of discussed topic through oral presentations, recitations, and games.	4.00	HIGHLY PRACTICED
13. I ask the learners to demonstrate what they have learned through activities that will require them to use of new media (podcasts, discord, etc.).	2.20	SOMEWHAT PRACTICED

Table 4 shows that teachers in English Learning Area highly practice indicator 11th and 12th with a mean average score of 4.0 while the 13th indicator which is asking the learners to demonstrate what they have learned through activities that will require them to use of new media is somewhat practiced with a mean average of 2.20.

The outcome does not support the findings of a study mentioned above conducted in 2015 by Kaur and Sudhar, which found that positive effects on the use of technology in the classroom, and shifts away from the passive listening style of instruction that has been prevalent in many Malaysian classrooms for the previous few decades.

The findings indicate that teachers in the English learning area highly practice traditional methods, such as letting students discuss a subject in an original way through role playing, games, jingles, and video presentations, and assessing students' retention of the material through oral presentations, recitations, and games. However, they still need to improve on using new media in their teaching methods.

Table 5 Philosophy and FCL Department

STATEMENTS	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTOR
9. I let the learners make decisions, elicit experiences on the topic, and utilize technology in their outputs.	3.85	HIGHLY PRACTICED
14. I let the students share their works in various platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Blogspot, Word Press, Pinterest, YouTube etc.	2.85	PRACTICED
15. I provide opportunities for meaningful interaction, enumerate significant points, and reflects on the significance through creative presentations.	3.85	HIGHLY PRACTICED

Table 5 shows that teachers in Philosophy and FCL Learning Area highly practice letting the learners make decisions, elicit experiences on the topic, and utilize technology in their outputs and providing opportunities for meaningful interaction, enumerate significant points, and reflects on the significance through creative presentations with a mean of 3.85 while letting the students share their works in various platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Blogspot, Word Press, Pinterest, YouTube etc is being practiced with a mean average of 2.85.

In the study of Tricamo (2021), it was concluded that by incorporating multiliteracies students will be able to create complex ideas through different modes, to collaborate, think creatively and create synthesis.

The findings show that instructors in the Philosophy and FCL Learning Areas make extensive use of technology in their classes, incorporating it into student work and discussions as well.

B. Proposed guideline for lesson planning

Guideline for Multimodal Lesson Planning Considering Audio, Visual, Spatial, and Linguistic Skills of Learners;

➤ Set clear learning objectives

- Define specific, quantifiable learning goals that cover the various modalities of language, visual, auditory, and spatial skills.
- Match curriculum standards with learning objectives, and take into account how each modality helps to achieve the intended results.
- Think about the particular multiliteracies abilities you wish your students to acquire, such as linguistic, audio, visual, and spatial mode.

➤ Selecting Content and Resources

- Select materials and content that showcase a range of cultural viewpoints, communication styles, and formats.
- Use a range of media to engage students with varying learning styles and aptitudes, such as text, graphics, audio, video, and interactive digital resources.

➤ Creating Activities for Multimodal Learning

- Give students the chance to design and produce their own multimodal texts, including infographics, podcasts, videos, blogs, and digital presentations.

➤ Activate Prior Knowledge

- To improve engagement and comprehension, draw on students' existing knowledge and experiences in the areas of audio, visual, spatial, and language modalities.
- Motivate students to make links between newly learned material and what they already know in a variety of modalities.

➤ Promoting Critical Engagement

- Encourage students to examine and assess multimedia texts for bias, credibility, and purpose in order to cultivate critical thinking and media literacy skills.
- Aid in the development of students' ability to evaluate and produce media messages in an ethical and responsible manner.

V. CONCLUSION

In the findings of multiliteracies, the teachers from different learning areas highly practice the use of multimodality in their lessons. The following conclusions were derived:

- The study found that there are aspects of multiliteracies that are highly practiced and others that are somewhat practiced at all. This demonstrates the need for educators to keep upgrading and developing since students of the twenty-first century require educators with these kinds of skills.
- The processes of teaching and learning are complicated by the fact that every classroom contains a diverse group of students with varying intelligences and learning styles. Teachers need to put in more effort as learners in order to keep providing high-quality instruction.

RECOMMENDATION

- Using multiliteracies as a framework for lesson design will help meet the goal of helping students comprehend and make sense of every topic they are taught.
- Teachers should provide a range of methods so that students can fully absorb all of the information because many subjects are new to them in senior high school. They might design exercises or exhibits that support the meanings of language, art, music, gesture, tactile perception, and space.
- The efficient application of multiliteracies in all subject areas needs to be the focus of future research.

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